

Reaction of Ethyl Chloroglyoxalate Arylhydrazones with Heterocyclic Amidine and Difunction Amino Derivatives

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The ethyl chloroglyoxalate *p*-tolylhydrazones (1) react with 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole, 3-aminotriazole and 2-aminobenzimidazole in triethylamine solution to give the corresponding pyrazolo[4,5-*c*]pyrazole (9), triazolo[4,5-*c*]triazole (12) and benzimidazolylamidrazone derivatives (14), respectively. The reaction mechanism has been suggested as 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of nitrileimine or alkylation reaction. Also the hydrazidoyl chlorides (1) react with *o*-phenylenediamine, *o*-aminophenol and anthranilic acid in DMF/triethylamine to give benzotriazine, benzoxazine and benzotriazipinone derivatives (18, 20 and 23), respectively. The structural assignments are based on elemental analysis and spectral data.

HYDRAZIDOYL halides are the reactive intermediates and their utility in heterocyclic synthesis has drawn considerable attention^{1,2}. In continuation of our program directed for development of new procedures for synthesis of fused azoles³⁻⁵, we report here the results of our investigation on the reactivity of hydrazidoyl chlorides towards cyclic amidines and *ortho*-substituted-anilines. Ethyl chloroglyoxalate *p*-tolylhydrazone (1) reacted with 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole in ethanolic triethylamine solution to give a product with molecular formula C₂₀H₁₈N₄O₂. Two possible isomeric structures (6 and 9) are considered (Scheme 1). Structure 6 was excluded on the basis of ¹H nmr spectra, which reveal the absorption of ester group and no resonance at δ 6.1 characteristic of pyrazole proton at C-4. Structure 9 is suggested for the product. Its formation is assumed to proceed either via alkylation of the pyrazole followed by subsequent cyclisation (route A) or via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to the nitrileimine (2) generated via base-catalysed elimination of hydrogen chloride (route B). It seems likely that the reaction pathway follows route B because we could not trace any of the intermediates (3-7) in the mother liquor.

On the other hand, ethyl chloroglyoxalate *p*-tolylhydrazone (1) reacts with cyclic amidines such as 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole in DMF-triethylamine solution. Two possible isomeric structures (12 and 13) are considered (Scheme 1). The assignment of structure 13 is based on the ¹H nmr spectra which reveal triazole protons downfield affected by ester group. Formation of compound 13 is assumed to proceed via alkylation of triazole at nitrogen atom of 2-position followed by cyclisation to 13, through loss of ammonia (pathway i).

Similarly, 1 was reacted with 2-aminobenzimidazole under the same reaction conditions to give a product with molecular formula C₁₅H₁₅N₅O₂.

Scheme 1

Two possible isomeric structures (14 and 15) are considered (Scheme 1). The structures could not be differentiated through ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. Structure 14 could be more probable because if 15 is obtained under the same reaction it could be cyclised into 16 through the loss of ammonia.

The reaction of the hydrazidoyl chloride with phenols and thiophenols has been reported^{5,6}. The

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present paper deals with the reaction of **1** with difunctional compounds. The alkylation reaction of the hydrazidoyl chloride (**1**) and *o*-phenylenediamine in DMF/triethylamine occurred at one of the amino groups to give the intermediate **17**, which cyclised under reaction conditions to give the benzotriazine derivative (**18**) through the loss of ammonia (Scheme 2).

The reaction of **1** with *o*-aminophenol may proceed via two alternative pathways, (iii) or (iv) (Scheme 2). If alkylation occurs at the OH group, the benzoxiazine derivative (**20**) may be obtained through an intermediate **19** by the loss of ammonia, while alkylation at the NH₂ group leads to the formation of the benzotriazine derivative (**18**) through dehydration of the intermediate **21**. Compound **18** is obtained from the reaction of **1** with *o*-phenylenediamine. Comparison of the product from **1** and *o*-aminophenol with **18** (previously obtained) shows that they are different, hence compound **18** is ruled out and compound **20** is suggested as the final product.

Finally, the hydrazidoyl chloride (**1**) was reacted with anthranilic acid under the same reaction conditions. The reaction proceeds via alkylation giving rise to an intermediate **22**, which through dehydration is converted into the benzotriazipine derivative (**23**) (Scheme 2). The structure suggested

for **23** is inferred from elemental analysis and spectral data.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye- Unicam SP-1100 spectrometer, and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian 60 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. Analytical data were obtained from the Cairo University.

Pyrazolo[4,5-c]pyrazole derivative (9): To a suspension of hydrazidoyl chloride (**1**; 0.1 mol) and 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole (0.1 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was added triethylamine (0.12 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was triturated with cold water. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give yellow powder (**9**; 60%), m.p. 178° (Found: C, 69.1; H, 5.1; N, 15.9. C₂₀H₁₃N₄O₂ (346) calcd. for: C, 69.4; H, 5.2; N, 16.2%); ν_{max} 3 000–3 300 (NH) and 1 710 cm⁻¹ (ester); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.3 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.1 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.2–8.0 (9H, m, ArH) and 10.9 (1H, s, NH).

General method to prepare 12, 14, 18, 20 and 23: A suspension of equimolar amounts (0.1 mol) of 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole/2-aminobenzimidazole/*o*-phenylenediamine/*o*-aminophenol/anthranilic acid and ethyl chloroglyoxalate *p*-tolylhydrazone (**1**) in DMF (30 ml) was treated with triethylamine (0.12 mol) and the reaction mixture was refluxed 5 h. The solid product was separated while hot (in case of **12, 18** and **20**) or by dilution with ice-water (in case of **14** and **23**), and then filtered and recrystallised from the proper solvent to yield **12, 14, 18, 20** and **23**, respectively.

Triazolo[4,5-c]triazole derivative (12): It gave yellowish green crystals, (70%), m.p. >250° (Found: C, 57.5; H, 4.6; N, 25.5. C₁₃H₁₃N₅O₂ (271) calcd. for: C, 57.6; H, 4.8; N, 25.8%); ν_{max} 1 720 cm⁻¹ (ester); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.1 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, q, CH₂) and 7.1–7.9 (4H, m, ArH).

Benzimidazolylamidrazone derivative (14): It gave yellow powder, (55%), m.p. 150° (Found: C, 63.9; H, 5.5; N, 20.5. C₁₃H₁₀N₅O₂ (337) calcd. for: C, 64.1; H, 5.6; N, 20.8%); ν_{max} 1 710 (ester) and 3 100–3 350 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.1 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.2–8.0 (8H, m, ArH), 10.1 (1H, s, NH) and 11.3 (1H, s, NH).

Benzotriazine derivative (18): It gave yellowish green crystals, (80%), m.p. >250° (Found: C, 68.9; H, 5.5; N, 14.1. C₁₇H₁₇N₃O₂ (295) calcd. for: C, 69.1; H, 5.8; N, 14.2%); ν_{max} 1 720 (ester) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.2–8.1 (8H, m, ArH) and 10.8 (1H, s, NH).

Benzoxazine derivative (20): It gave orange crystals, (75%), m.p. 185° (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.3; N, 9.3. C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₃ (294) calcd. for: C, 69.3;

Scheme 2

H, 5.4; N, 9.5%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 710 cm^{-1} (ester); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.2 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.1 (2H, q, CH_2) and 7.1–8.0 (8H, m, ArH).

Benzotriazipinone derivative (23): It gave yellow powder, (59%), m.p. 138° (Found: C, 66.6; H, 5.1; N, 12.8. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_8$ (323) calcd. for: C, 66.9; H, 5.3; N, 13.0%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 710 (ester), 1 670 (C=O) and 3 150 cm^{-1} (NH); δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.2 (3H, t, CH_3), 2.4 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.2 (2H, q, CH_2), 7.2–8.0 (8H, m, ArH) and 11.1 (1H, s, NH).

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